

Prevention and Treatment of rUTI Guidelines and Nurse Feedback

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Background

- UTIs are prevalent among the elderly, with a prevalence rate of 0 to 13. 6% annually.
- Inconsistent and ineffective clinical guidelines rUTI in this elderly population
- Increased antibiotic resistance among geriatric populations, UTI accounts for many antibiotics prescribed in primary care.
- rUTI in geriatrics accounts for increased mortality rates and decreased quality of life

Project Statement

- Conduct a systematic literature review to develop clinical guidelines to improve the prevention and treatment of rUTIs in SNF residents.
- Identify staff perception of the new revised clinical guidelines.
- Pilot rUTI clinical guidelines for three months to reduce the rate to less than 5% within three months.

Methods

- Focus on nurse response and feedback to newly installed guidelines
- 30–40-minute educational meetings outside regular nursing activities
- The setting was in an SNF in Los Angeles with a capacity for 300 patients
- Weekly consultation would occur with the staff
- Methods were measured through qualitative means of participant feedback, clarification requests, and compliance with the guidelines

References

Theoretical Framework- Iowa Model

- To further legitimate this project's theoretical framework, the IEBPM directed the design and implementation process.
- The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice is step-by-step guide to clinical practices using evidence-based research to enhance current policies and was implemented in this project.
- The model cooperated with existing knowledge of UTI prevention of nursing and other clinical staff.

Analysis and Discussion

- There was a slight but gradual change in the reported number of rUTI cases among the residents across the 6 -month period.
- The first three months (October-December), the total reported rUTI was 28 cases.
- Final three months (January-March), the total reported rUTI was 26 cases.
- Reduction in UTI rates appears to correlate with the intervention period. However, unclear whether the reduction in UTI cases was clinically significant.

Nurses Feedback

Nurses feedback on likelihood of using the New Clinical Guideline

- ❖ 85% believe the new guideline is easy to use, while 14% believe it requires more clarity.
- ❖ On a scale of 10, half of the nurses rated the guideline 10, 4% rated it 9, 10% rated it 8, 7% rated it 7, and 10% rated it 6. However, 17% of nurses rated the guideline 5 and below.

Instruments

- Data collection was through Qualtrics, an online survey software
- The questions included text entry, graphic slider, allow one answer and Likert-type. The survey was distributed through QR codes, ensuring participants responded once

Revised Guideline

Incorporated three preventative measures that seemed to be missing in the current guideline, namely,

- (1) Hydration
- (2) Hygiene
- (3) Catheter management

Limitations

- Small sample size.
- It is unclear whether the participants constitute a representative sample of nursing staff at the facility.
- In addition, some of the responses from the staffers in the SNF were in Spanish

Recommendations

- Weekly qualitative discussions on how the McGeer Model Implementation is in practice
- Create real-time feedback loops to identify possible shortfalls in operational effectiveness.
- Provide adequate training on the use of effective evidence-based UTI management strategies
- Report rates of UTI and the interventions implemented to determine if the interventions are effective.
- implement the revised McGeer guideline with particular attention to the evidence-based components.